

Original Article in Clinical Psychology

Causal Model of Suicidal Thoughts in Adolescents Living in Welfare Organizations Based on Emotional Intelligence and Meaning in Life with the Mediation of Perceived Social Support

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Abstract

Introduction: This study aimed to design a causal model of suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's State Welfare Organization (SWO), based on emotional intelligence (EI) and meaning in life, with the mediating role of perceived social support (PSS).

Methods A descriptive-correlational study with structural equation modeling (SEM) was conducted among 320 adolescents (155 girls, 165 boys) living in SWO centers. Sampling was performed using multistage random cluster sampling. Standardized tools included the Ask Suicide-Screening Questions (ASQ), Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS), Meaning in Life Questionnaire (MLQ), and Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS). Data were analyzed with SPSS and AMOS software.

Results: EI ($\beta = -0.107$, $p < 0.05$) and meaning in life ($\beta = -0.242$, $p < 0.01$) were negatively associated with suicidal thoughts. PSS mediated the relationship between EI and meaning in life with suicidal thoughts ($\beta = -0.586$, $p < 0.001$). The final model explained 69% of the variance in suicidal thoughts, and the fit indices indicated a satisfactory fit.

Conclusions: Higher EI and a stronger sense of meaning in life reduce suicidal ideation among adolescents in SWO centers, with PSS serving as a significant protective mediator.

Keywords: Adolescents; Emotional intelligence; Meaning in life; Perceived social support; Suicidal thoughts.

Cite this paper as: Yousefi RN, Davari R, Roshan MJ. Causal Model of Suicidal Thoughts in Adolescents Living in Welfare Organizations Based on Emotional Intelligence and Meaning in Life with the Mediation of Perceived Social Support. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2026;3(2):174–192. doi:10.5281/zenodo.18075472

Received: 28 February 2025; Revised:18 April 2025; Accepted: 30 August 2025; Published Online: 28 December 2025

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a sensitive period in life with rapid physical, mental, and social changes, which can bring threats due to its inevitable fluctuations and conflicts. In other words, the dangers of this course can change the course of a teenager's personal, professional, and family life due to the entrance to youth and gaining identity. One of the biggest problems of this period is suicidal thoughts. Although suicide is seen among all age groups, it can have irreparable consequences in adolescence due to poor control over life, feelings of social loneliness, problems with parents and friends, and weakness in problem-solving and emotion management [1].

Although Iran ranks 58th in the world with a suicide rate of 6 people per 100,000 people, it is necessary to address this psychological-social variable [2]. Suicide is one of the mental health problems. More attention has been paid to the category of suicide in developed countries, on the other hand, this issue is not given importance in developing countries, and the suicide situation in more than half of the developing countries of the world, statistics does not exist [3]. Suicidal thoughts are the result of mental preoccupations, which range from fleeting thoughts about the worthlessness of life and the wish for death to putting it into practice for self-destruction. Attempting suicide always starts with thinking about self-destruction [4]. Although suicide is seen among all age groups, it causes the loss of useful years of life in adolescents, which is very important. It seems that adolescents feel weaker in moments of life when they face personal problems, and this is when they think that there is no way back. Contrary to what most adults think, most adolescent suicide attempts are pre-planned actions, not impulsive reactions to failure [5]. In many countries, the highest rate of suicide is attributed to adolescents and young people. Globally, it is the second leading cause of death between the ages of 15 and 29 [6]. Also, the results of the comparison of 49 developing countries reported the average overall prevalence of suicidal thoughts as 19.8%. Approximately one-third of adolescents who have suicidal thoughts plan to commit suicide during their teenage years. About 60% of the people who plan such a plan, usually commit suicide one year after the thought of suicide starts in their mind[6]. According to the results of a study in Iran, 39% of adolescents suffer from emotional and behavioral problems and their mental health is not favorable [7]. Although few scientific and systematic studies have been conducted in the field of suicide in Iran, the data shows an increasing trend, especially in girls [5]. On the other hand, researches conducted in different parts of Iran show that the highest rate of suicide is in the age group of 10 to 20 years[8]. In the field of the etiology of suicidal thoughts, several factors have been identified so far, which can be classified into 3 categories: personal-psychological factors, family factors, and socio-cultural factors.

The ability to adapt to the environment is one of the effective factors in creating life expectancy and preventing suicide. The ability to adopt adaptive or creative behaviors is one of the common concepts of intelligence among psychologists. Emotional intelligence (EI) also known as Emotional Quotient (EQ), is one of the types of intelligence that is not only the factor of controlling emotional responses but also the factor of controlling the appropriate use of emotions in situations. It can be an important predictor for success in personal, family, and workplace relationships, and it causes the improvement and modification of professional activities of the job position and the acquisition of

necessary and desirable skills [9]. EI determines how to interact and deal with everyday issues incidents and sudden situations that a person encounters. Therefore, the experience of stress occurs only when that situation is evaluated as damage, loss, threat, or raisin. What is important in this is the way a person evaluates the situation and the process of dealing with these stresses; more precisely, it is the use of stress coping styles that can reduce the impact of stress on a person's mental health. Otherwise, negative thinking styles and ineffective coping styles may lead to depression, delinquency anti-social behavior, and in the worst case, suicidal thoughts and even suicide. Vulnerable people and groups are those people who cannot take care of themselves against physical, psychological, and social harm [10].

Experts who believe in EI argue that mental intelligence is not enough to form a person's personality and existence. Therefore, to get a more complete picture of a person's ability to make appropriate decisions, the effective use of interpersonal skills to communicate and understand others, the tools of self-existence suitably and proportionately, and managing stress efficiently and properly, the presence of EI is essential [11]. EI is an ability to understand, understand, and manage emotions is very important and has a positive impact on many individual components and can have direct or indirect effects on various factors [12].

In recent years, positive psychology has conducted studies on finding meaning in life as a protective factor against suicide [13, 14]. Researchers reported that finding meaning in life is one of the protective factors against suicide attempts and increases positive attitudes toward life [15]. Finding meaning in life is a universal human goal that is tied to individual identity and allows people to cope with difficult situations. [16]. The best model of meaning in life divides it into two components: the search for meaning in life and the presence of meaning in life. People who have not yet found the meaning of life may be searching for it. However, people who have achieved the meaning of life may seek to achieve a broader or different meaning [17]. Finding meaning in life has been proposed as a factor in coping with pressures and reducing pathological behaviors. The relationship between the lack of meaning in life and various pathological behaviors has been experimentally investigated [16]. Empirically, the lack of meaning in life is related to a wide range of harmful behaviors such as drug abuse, delinquency, anxiety, depression, and suicidal tendencies [16,17]. There is a purpose and a meaning in life, and this purpose is such that it gives meaning to even the most difficult moments of life. Death, suffering, disease, and natural disasters become bearable by considering the meaning of life. [18] emphasizes people's search for meaning in life and believes that if a person cannot find meaning in her life, he/she will feel empty and disappointed in life, and boredom and fatigue will cover his/her whole being.

PSS is among other factors related to suicidal thoughts in adolescents. One of the psychological features that is very important in adolescence is PSS. It is defined as a person realizing that his beliefs and feelings are given importance by others and considered a valuable person [19]. Understanding PSS is more important than receiving it. In other words, a person's understanding and attitude towards the received support is more important than the amount of support provided to him [20]. Also, in the classification of dimensions and people related to PSS, it is stated that PSS includes the help and support of family (PSS-Fa), friends (PSS-Fr), and other important people in life, which a person understands according to his/her social and personal conditions [21]. PSS refers to a mental feeling of belonging, being accepted, and being loved. Support is a relationship for every person and creates a sense of intimacy and closeness. PSS is a two-way help that creates a positive image of the individual, self-acceptance, and a feeling of love and worth. All these features give a person the opportunity for self-actualization and growth [22].

Based on what has been said, the aim of the present study is to answer this question: Does the gender factor moderate the relationship between EI and finding meaning in life and suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in SWO centers, taking into account the mediating role of PSS?

METHODS

In this study, the research design was a structural equation modeling (SEM) design. The statistical population of this research included young females and males living in Tehran's SWO centers in 2023. Due to the large size of the statistical population and the impossibility of accessing and obtaining permission to enter all quasi-family centers, a multistage random sampling technique was used.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria: (i) 15 to 18 years old, (ii) not being unsupervised or poorly supervised, and (iii) living in SWO centers.

Exclusion criteria: (i) suffering from mental illnesses, and (ii) receiving drug therapy and psychotherapy interventions.

Procedures

Ask Suicide-Screening Questions (ASQ)

The ASQ is a 15-item self-report suicide risk–screening measure and was designed by [23]. Its main purpose is to evaluate the tendency or probability of suicide in adolescents. Each question has two options. The yes option gets a score of one and the no option gets a score of zero. Of course, this scoring method will be reversed for questions 1, 5, and 11. In adolescents who have a strong desire to commit suicide, the answers will be as follows:

1. No, 2. Yes, 3. Yes, 4. Yes, 5. No, 6. Yes, 7. Yes, 8. Yes, 9. Yes, 10. Yes, 11. No, 12. Yes, 13. Yes

[24] found the validity of the questionnaire to be 0.65. Also, the reliability of the ASQ in adolescents was calculated using Cronbach's alpha method equal to 0.69, which indicates the acceptable reliability of this questionnaire [25].

Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS)

The EI questionnaire was designed and compiled by [26] to measure EI, from the point of view of [27]. In addition to international support, this scale is easy to administer because it is a scale with a small number of items. Specifically, it includes 16 items of the 7-point Likert type (1 = Strongly disagree to 7 = Strongly agree), which are divided into four dimensions: Appraisal and expression of emotion in the self (self-emotional appraisal [SEA]), Appraisal and recognition of emotion in others (others' emotional appraisal [OEA]), Regulation of emotion in the self (regulation of emotion [ROE]), and Use of emotion to facilitate performance (use of emotion [UOE]). Examples for each dimension are SEA ("I have a good sense of why I feel certain feelings most of the time"), OEA ("I am a good observer of others' emotions"), UOE ("I always set goals for myself and then try my best to achieve them"), and ROE ("I can always calm down quickly when I am very angry."). [28], has evaluated the content validity, formal validity, and criteria of WLEIS and estimated the calculated Cronbach's alpha coefficient above 0.7.

The Meaning in Life Questionnaire (MLQ)

The MLQ was created by [29]. It has 10 items, which include two subscales: The Presence of Meaning and The Search for Meaning. They consist of five items each. The Presence of Meaning subscale measures how fully respondents feel their lives are of meaning. The subscale of the presence of meaning includes these items: I understand the meaning of my life; I have found a satisfying purpose for my life; My life has a clear sense of purpose; I am looking for something that makes my life meaningful; I am looking for a purpose and ideal for my life. The Search for Meaning subscale measures how engaged and motivated respondents are in efforts to find meaning or deepen their understanding of meaning in their lives. The search for meaning subscale includes the following items: Items in my life I have a clear sense of purpose; I have a good feeling that something gives meaning to my life; I have always been looking for a purpose for my life; I have always been looking for something that gives meaning to my feeling of life; I am looking to find a purpose for my life. The MLQ assesses two dimensions of meaning in life using 10 items rated on a seven-point scale from "Absolutely True" to "Absolutely Untrue." The total scores of questions 2, 3, 7, 8, and 10 determine the level of a person's effort to find meaning and the total scores of questions 1, 4, 5, 6, and 9 (question 9

with reverse coding) determine the level of meaningfulness of a person's life. The MLQ has good reliability, test-retest stability, stable factor structure, and convergence among informants. According to [29], internal consistency was good for both the Presence (0.86) and Search (0.87) subscales. Also, the reliability was good for both the Presence (0.7) and Search (0.73) subscales. The test and retest reliability of MLQ in Iran was 0.84 for the Presence subscale and 0.74 for the Search subscale [30].

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS)

The MSPSS is a 12-item instrument and measures PSS from three sources: family, community, and friends on a seven-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). The minimum and maximum scores of the individual on the whole scale are 12 and 84, respectively, and in each of the family, social, and friend support subscales, 4 and 28 respectively. A higher score indicates greater PSS. The psychometric properties of the MSPSS have been confirmed in worldwide research. In a preliminary study, the psychometric properties of this scale in samples of Iranian students and general population $n = 742$; 311 students, 431 general, Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated for the whole scale and the items of the three subscales of family (PSS-Fa), friends (PSS-Fr), and other important people in life, were 0.91, 0.87, 0.83 and 0.89. These coefficients confirmed the internal consistency of the multidimensional scale of PSS [31].

Population target

Applied research with a descriptive-correlational design (SEM). Participants: 320 adolescents (15–18 years old) living in Tehran SWO centers in 2023. Sampling: multistage cluster random.

Inclusion criteria: Age 15–18, living in SWO centers, not poorly supervised.

Exclusion criteria: Diagnosed mental illness, receiving drug therapy or psychotherapy.

Sampling procedure and study instruments

- ASQ [23,24]
- WLEIS [26]
- MLQ [29]
- MSPSS [32]

Statistical analysis

Normality (Skewness, Kurtosis), collinearity (VIF, tolerance), CFA, and SEM with AMOS.

Ethical aspects

Approved by the Ethics Committee of Islamic Azad University, Tehran Central Branch (Code: IR.IAU.CTB.REC.1402.167). Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

RESULTS

In the present study, 320 adolescents living in Tehran's SWO (155 girls and 165 boys) participated with the mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (S.D.) of the age group for females and males equal to 15.70 and 1.35 years, respectively. Table 1 shows the mean, S.D., and correlation coefficients between the variables of EI (SEA, OEA, ROE, and UOE), finding meaning in life, PSS (PSS-Fa, PSS-Fr and PSS-others), and suicidal thoughts. As shown in Table 1, the correlation between the variables was in the expected direction and aligned with the theories of the research field.

Univariate normal distribution

In this research, to evaluate the assumption of univariate normal distribution, Kurtosis, and Skewness of the variables and to evaluate the assumption of collinearity of values, variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance coefficient were investigated. (Table 2).

As shown in Table 2, the Kurtosis and Skewness values of all components are in the range of ± 2 . This indicates that the assumption of univariate normal distribution among the data is valid [33]. Also, as shown in Table 2, the assumption of collinearity was valid among the data of the current research. Because the tolerance coefficient values of predictor variables were larger than 0.1 and the VIF values of each of them were smaller than 10. According to [34], the tolerance coefficient is less than 0.1 and the value of the variance inflation factor is higher than 10, indicating that the assumption of collinearity is not established.

Table 1. The mean, S.D., and correlation coefficients between research variables.

Research variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. EI - SEA	-									
2. EI - OEA	-	-								
	0.71									
	**									
3. EI - UOE	0.	-0.	-							
	65**	65**								
4. EI - ROE	0.	0.42*	-0.	-						
	45**	*	57**							
5. Finding meaning in life-The Presence	0.	0.33*	0.46*	-0.	-					
	27**	*	*	43**						
6. Finding meaning in life-The Search	0.	0.24*	0.41*	0.29*	-0.	-				
	23**	*	*	*	48**					
7. PSS-Fa	0.	0.29*	0.40*	0.25*	0.32*	-0.	-			
	22**	*	*	*	*	71**				
8. PSS-Fr	0.	0.39*	0.46*	0.34*	0.66*	0.45*	-0.	-		
	30**	*	*	*	*	*	35**			
9. PSS-others	0.	0.33*	0.48*	0.45*	0.75*	0.53*	0.39*	-0.	-	
	32**	*	*	*	*	*	*	71**		
10. Suicidal thoughts	-	-0.	-0.	-0.	-0.	-0.	-0.	-0.	-0.	-
	0.35	36**	54**	36**	63**	61**	48**	56**	62**	
	**									
Mean	1	11.92	11.01	10.09	16.26	19.35	10.90	11.5	10.6	7.6
	1.81							5	3	7
S.D.	3.	3.55	3.72	3.05	4.39	5.65	3.68	3.79	3.40	2.1
	19									7

Table 2. Examining the assumptions of normality and collinearity.

Research variables	Univariate normality		Collinearity of values	
	Skewness	Kurtosis	Tolerance coefficient	VIF
1. EI - SEA	-0.06	-1.33	0.43	2.32
2. EI - OEA	-0.02	-0.97	0.39	2.54
3. EI - UOE	0.27	-0.83	0.36	2.75
4. EI - ROE	0.50	-0.91	0.61	1.64
5. Finding meaning in life-The Presence	0.59	-0.03	0.41	2.46

6. Finding meaning in life– The Search	0.46	-0.66	0.47	2.14
7. PSS-Fa	0.23	-1.13	0.39	2.60
8. PSS-Fr	-0.07	-0.63	0.42	2.36
9. PSS- others	-0.39	-0.90	0.39	3.09
10. Suicidal thoughts	0.46	-0.59	-	-

Multivariate normal distribution

In this research, to evaluate the establishment or non-establishment of the assumption of multivariate normal distribution (MND), the information analysis related to "The Mahalanobis distance" was used. The values of Skewness and Kurtosis were obtained as 1.05 and 0.81, respectively. Therefore, the value of both indices was in the range of ± 2 , which shows that confirms the assumption of MND among the data. Finally, to evaluate the homogeneity of variances, the scatter diagram of the standardized residuals of the errors was examined and the evaluations showed that the assumption is also valid among the data.

Model analysis

a. Model Specification

In the research measurement model, 9 indicators were considered to reflect 3 existing structures.

According to Figure 1, it was assumed that the indicators of SEA, OEA, UOE, and ROE are the latent variables of EI. The indicators of the presence of meaning and the search for meaning are the latent variables of finding meaning in life. Also, the indicators of PSS-Fa, PSS-Fr, and PSS-others measure the latent variable of PSS. The measurement model fit was assessed using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), AMOS 24.0 software, and maximum likelihood (ML) estimation. Table 3 shows the fit indices of measurement and structural models. The initial model of the modified model

Table 3. Fit indices of the research model.

Fitness indicators	Model			Cutting points
	Measuring		Structural	
	Initial	Modified		
Chi-square	99.29	57.82	69.41	-
Degrees of freedom (d.f.)	24	23	29	-
Normed chi-square (χ^2/df)	4.14	2.51	2.29	< 3
Goodness Fit Index (GFI)	0.930	0.960	0.957	< 0.9
Adjusted Goodness Fit Index (AGFI)	0.869	0.921	0.919	< 0.85
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.952	0.978	0.979	< 0.9
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.099	0.069	0.066	> 0.08

Table 3 shows that the RMSEA fit index obtained from the CFA does not support the acceptable fit of the measurement model with the collected data. Considering the importance of that index in fitting the model with the data, the evaluation indices are modified, and based on that, by creating covariance between the two indicators of SEA and OEA, and modifying the measurement model, the acceptable fit indices for the measurement model were obtained. In the measurement model, the largest factor loading belonged to the presence of meaning indicator ($\beta=0.944$) and the smallest factor load belonged to ROE ($\beta=0.622$). Thus, considering that the factor loadings of all indicators were greater than 0.32, it can be said that all of them had the necessary power to measure the current research variables.

b. Structural model

Following the evaluation of the measurement model fit, in the second stage, the fit indices of SEM were estimated and evaluated. In the SEM, it was assumed that finding meaning in life and EI are related to the mediation of PSS with

suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO. Table 3 shows that the fit indices obtained from the analysis support the range of acceptable values of SEM with the collected data. Table 4 shows the PCs in the SEM.

Table 4. The PC of direct effects, indirect effects, and total effects between research variables.

Path	b	S.E.	β	p
Finding meaning ---> PSS	0.431	0.03	0.431	0.001
EI ---> PSS	0.386	0.073	0.386	0.001
PSS ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.071	-	0.001
	0.586		0.586	
Direct PC of the finding meaning ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.033	-	0.001
	0.242		0.242	
Direct PC of EI ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.063	-	0.067
	0.107		0.107	
Indirect PC of the finding meaning ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.036	-	0.001
	0.135		0.253	
Indirect PC of EI ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.081	-	0.001
	0.251		0.226	
Total PC of the finding meaning ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.033	-	0.001
	0.264		0.495	
Total PC of EI ---> Suicidal thoughts	-	0.075	-	0.001
	0.371		0.332	

Table 4 shows that the total PC (total of direct and indirect PC) between finding meaning in life ($\beta=-0.495$, $P=0.001$) and EI ($\beta=-0.332$, $P=0.001$) was negative and significant with suicidal thoughts. Also, The PC between PSS and suicidal thoughts was negative and significant ($p=0.001$, $\beta=0.586$). The indirect PC between finding meaning in life ($\beta=-0.253$, $P=0.001$) and EI ($\beta=-0.226$, $P=0.001$) with suicidal thoughts were negative and significant. This finding shows that in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO, the PSS mediates the relationship between finding meaning in life and EI with suicidal thoughts in a negative and significant way. Figure 1 shows the standard parameters in the SEM of the research.

Figure 1. Standard parameters of the modified research model.

Figure 1 shows the standard parameters in the research model. As shown, the sum of squared multiple correlation (R^2) for suicidal thoughts was equal to 0.69. This shows that the suicidal thoughts factors of finding meaning in life, EI, and PSS explain a total of 69% of the variance of suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO.

DISCUSSION

First hypothesis: *EI is related to suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO.*

The results showed that the total PC between EI and suicidal thoughts is negative and significant. Therefore, in the test of the first hypothesis, it was concluded that EI has a negative and significant relationship with suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in SWO. These results are consistent with the findings of other researchers [35- 41].

The findings of [35] support the significant relationship and negative correlation between EI and suicidal thoughts. Their research showed that a person's ability to manage his emotions has a strong relationship with suicidal thoughts. In addition, emotional cognition and other emotional management skills are somewhat predictive of suicidal thoughts. [36] consider low EI as one of the reasons for increasing suicidal thoughts in depressed patients. The findings of [37], confirmed the positive and significant relationship between EI and adaptive emotion cognitive regulation (ACER) strategies and the negative relationship with suicidal thoughts among adolescents. Those adolescents with higher EI were more likely to report more ACER strategies, which in turn predicted lower levels of suicidal ideation. [42] showed that ACER strategies play a mediating role in the relationship between EI and well-being, and the use of maladaptive emotion regulation strategies and poor ability to regulate emotions increases the risk of suicidal thoughts. Poor EI and difficulty in regulating mood are related to the increased risk of suicidal thoughts and suicidal behavior in people dependent on alcohol consumption, and emotional dysregulation predicts a higher prevalence of suicidal thoughts [38]. There is a significant relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts and mental health of 15-17-year-old adolescents [39] and a high level of EI plays an important role in protecting against suicidal thoughts and suicidal behaviors [40, 41] showed that compared to normal students, students with suicidal thoughts have lower EI and resilience and use more ineffective coping styles.

EI, which is defined as a set of hierarchically organized emotional skills for perceiving, using, understanding, and regulating emotions, plays an important role in preventing suicidal behavior/thoughts during adolescence. One of the important aspects that usually triggers emotions and suicidal thoughts is the difficulty in expressing and regulating emotions [43]. According to psychological theories, suicidal thoughts, and suicidal behavior come from the inability to

moderate and tolerate negative experiences and experience unpleasant emotions. From this point of view, committing suicide may be an attempt to escape from these experiences. Those who have better skills in managing their emotions may be less exposed to suicidal thoughts and risk in response to stress [36].

According to the researchers, the relationship between EI and the development and use of effective cognitive, emotional, and behavioral strategies, by helping people cope with stress and negative events, leads to higher mental health and well-being and lower levels of suicidal thoughts and suicide [37]. Research shows that EI can affect mental health by improving the ability to manage life's stresses. Those with higher EI may use more effective coping strategies that lead to reduced suicidal thoughts and, as a result, improved mental health [14].

Low EI has a direct relationship with poor problem-solving skills and suicidal thoughts and actions [44]. Also, high levels of rumination due to low EI may increase suicidal thoughts in adolescents. Adolescents who score lower on EI tests are more likely to struggle with low self-esteem and suicidal thoughts [45]. It seems that people with higher EI are likely to show better skills in interpersonal relationships, and because of their high ability to understand their own and others' emotions, they receive more psychological and PSS from others. EI helps people to get a better understanding of their emotions. This level of self-awareness can help identify early signs of depression and anxiety, such as feelings of hopelessness and emptiness, feelings of loneliness and isolation, and feelings of lack of control over existing conditions, and reduce high-risk behaviors such as suicide. From this point of view, EI is considered an efficient tool for preventing suicidal thoughts and helps people cope better with life's challenges.

EI and suicide risk are significantly influenced by complex interactions between different brain regions and neurotransmitters. The prefrontal cortex plays an important role in performing various tasks such as emotion regulation, planning, problem-solving, decision-making, personality regulation, working memory, and impulse control. The prefrontal cortex is involved in inhibiting harmful behaviors, such as the inability to inhibit suicidal tendencies. Therefore, the immature functioning of the growing and developing brain in the prefrontal cortex and reduced activity in this area may lead adolescents to engage in risky activities such as suicide, violence, and drug addiction [46]. Both EI and suicidality are influenced by specific areas of the brain and neurotransmitters. Abnormal activity in the amygdala, which plays a role in processing emotions and emotional reactions, can lead to problems in EI and increase the risk of suicide. Another area that plays a role in learning and memory and helps regulate emotions is the hippocampus. According to research, changes in the size and function of the hippocampus may be associated with emotional problems and the risk of suicide [44]. Also, disorders in the dopaminergic system can affect EI and suicidal behaviors. Decreased serotonin levels are also associated with depression and increased risk of suicide. Changes in the level of norepinephrine, which is involved in the stress response, can affect mood and emotional behaviors. Disturbances in the dopaminergic system can affect EI and suicidal behaviors [37].

In this framework, suicidal thoughts are the result of the inability to analyze and adjust unpleasant and uncomfortable emotional states that are rooted in low EI. In the structure of EI, mood regulation plays an important role in reducing internal distress. Mood regulation is part of a complex emotional executive system including managing current emotional distress and predicting the emotional outcome based on past experiences. Therefore, it seems that high EI and skill in managing emotions and experiencing positive emotions can reduce suicidal thoughts. Also, good mood regulation skills probably increase the ability to experience and benefit from positive emotions. This not only reduces negative emotions but also improves social interactions and potentially reduces the impact of interpersonal issues on suicidal tendencies.

The second hypothesis: *Finding meaning in life is related to suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO.*

The results showed that the total PC between finding meaning in life and suicidal thoughts is negative and significant. Therefore, in the test of the second hypothesis, it was concluded that Finding meaning in life has a negative and significant relationship with suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in SWO. These results are consistent with the findings of other researchers [47- 57].

[47], showed that low levels of finding meaning in life, hope, and PSS have a negative and significant relationship with suicidal thoughts and increase the probability of using psychiatric drugs to attempt suicide in nursing students. According to [48], finding meaning in life and positive and negative emotions show distinct and complex links with the three dimensions of suicidal thoughts (pessimism, sleep, and despair). Finding meaning in life and positive affect act as a protective shield against suicidal thoughts. The findings of [49] showed that although finding meaning in life does not have a direct and significant relationship with suicidal thoughts, finding meaning in life through depression has the strongest relationship with suicidal thoughts. Finding meaning in life moderates the association between suicidal ideation, hopelessness, and borderline symptoms in individuals with eating disorders [50]. The presence of meaning in life can lead to a decrease in suicidal thoughts by increasing positive emotions [51,52]. [51,52] showed that finding meaning in life has a significant and negative relationship with suicidal thoughts and suicidal behavior in students. In a systematic review, [23] found that finding meaning in life is a protective factor against suicidal thoughts and suicidal behavior [54] also found that finding meaning in life partially mediates the relationship between mental health status and the severity of suicidal thoughts. Specifically, students who experience poorer mental health status may be more likely to report having a poorer sense of meaning in life, which in turn increases suicidal ideation. [55], showed that there is a negative and significant relationship between finding meaning in life and suicidal thoughts in the elderly. The presence of meaning in life by reducing the initially incompatible schemas leads to an increase in suicidal thoughts in students. Therefore, finding meaning in life is a protective factor against the risk of suicide in students [21,57], also showed that finding meaning in life and coping strategies can explain and predict suicidal thoughts in the elderly.

Finding meaning in life includes one's values, experiences, goals, and beliefs, and has an inverse relationship with depression, hopelessness, and suicidal thoughts [58]. Finding meaning in life is considered a factor in increasing resilience and strong flexibility [53]. People who feel confused about the meaning of life are prone to despair and suicidal thoughts. Individuals who reported having suicidal thoughts in the past 12 months were more likely to attempt suicide in the next 12 months [48]. Among the two dimensions of finding meaning in life - the search for meaning and the presence of meaning in life -, the presence of meaning in life may be the main and key factor in preventing suicide, while the search for the meaning of life may predict suicidal thoughts [52,59] found that having meaningful moments in life can reduce hopelessness. Thus, meaning in life may act as a barrier against various factors that fuel suicidal ideation, such as bullying victimization, psychological stress, hopelessness, and loss of sense of belonging.[48], present the presence of a complex interaction between emotion, finding meaning in life, and suicidal thoughts. Their findings showed that negative affect is related to despair, low sleep quality, and dimensions of pessimism in suicidal thoughts. In line with [48], it can be concluded that this close relationship between finding meaning in life and emotions shows that emotions can indirectly affect suicidal thoughts and emphasizes their importance as common factors influencing suicidal thoughts. The presence of meaning in life by helping to strengthen and improve hope improves mental well-being and reduces the feeling of hopelessness. As [47] showed, the existence of ideals and values can give meaning to a difficult life and increase the sense of duty and responsibility. Finding meaning in life can help people choose a set of appropriate goals, experience a sense of agency, and accept themselves. Probably, even in the face of failure, such a person can consider more suitable paths and move forward with more hope. The destructive effect of a sense of meaninglessness can leave people feeling what

[60] called an existential vacuum or existential frustration. The long-term experience of meaninglessness, characterized by boredom and apathy, may increase the tendency toward suicidal behavior.

In general, finding meaning in the lives of adolescents living in SWO can have a great impact on their mental health. So in the absence of this meaning, the possibility of suicidal thoughts increases. The absence of meaning in the lives of those who feel less belonging to others, maybe a factor for the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and even suicide attempts, combined with frequent traumatic experiences, the experience of feeling aimless, lonely, and isolated, lack of hope for the future, and feelings of worthlessness. The absence of meaning in the lives of those who feel less belonging to others, if combined with frequent traumatic experiences, the experience of aimlessness, loneliness, isolation, lack of hope for the future, and feelings of worthlessness, may be a factor for the emergence of suicidal thoughts and even actions to commit suicide. Therefore, providing opportunities to create meaning and purpose in the lives of this group of adolescents can help reduce the risk of suicidal thoughts and improve their mental health.

The third hypothesis: *PSS is related to suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO.*

The results showed that the PC between PSS and suicidal thoughts is negative and significant. Therefore, in the test of the third hypothesis, it was concluded that PSS has a negative and significant relationship with suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in SWO. These results are consistent with the findings of other researchers [60-66].

Poor PSS is a predictor of the severity of suicidal thoughts in students [60,61]. show that PSS provides greater protection against suicidal thoughts for people with lower levels of mental health symptoms. [62], indicated that negative judgments can devalue healthcare trainees' work and thus create a psychological burden for them, which is associated with emotional exhaustion, insomnia, and suicidal thoughts. By examining 818 studies, [63] support the existence of a significant negative relationship between PSS and suicidal thoughts in cancer patients and the key role of PSS in preventing suicidal thoughts in them. [67], showed that PSS-FA, and PSS-Fr, but not teachers, were inversely related to suicidal ideation in rural Chinese children experiencing rejection by others. [64], showed that there is a significant negative relationship between PSS and suicidal thoughts in high school students [65], also support the existence of a significant negative correlation between the components of PSS and life satisfaction with suicidal thoughts in students.

About half of patients who attempt or die by suicide do not disclose suicidal ideation [68]. Thus, higher levels of psychological distress can lead to increased isolation and social withdrawal as a way to express distress. Reduced interaction with others can cause feelings of loneliness [61]. In line with these findings, it seems that the risk of suicide is lower when a person has more social connections, and this emphasizes the importance of PSS. However, [69], believe that people experiencing distress and suicidal thoughts may hesitate to seek help due to fear of not being understood by their loved ones. According to these findings, for adolescents who are deprived of the possibility of receiving support from their family and siblings due to their living conditions, having a strong connection with a group can help increase the sense of belonging in people and promote the feeling of personal worth. Also, the existence of efficient social relations provides access to wider sources of PSS. In such an environment, people can monitor each other's behavior and have positive effects on each other's psychological well-being.

Those with lifetime suicidal ideation reported significantly less support from their family and felt more dissatisfied with this level of support [60]. Being able to share thoughts and knowing someone is available when needed seems to reduce people's feelings of loneliness. Talking about suicidal thoughts and the reactions and judgments of others can be difficult, daunting, and scary, so people may fear others' evaluations of themselves. People around them may also think that asking more about suicidal thoughts will lead adolescents to commit suicide more. [62], believe that asking people about suicidal thoughts helps to better understand what is happening and make a more informed decision.

According to [67], talking about suicidal thoughts with a child or teenager does not lead to fostering suicidal ideas and does not increase the risk of committing suicide.

PSS increases resilience, and resilience is considered one of the protective factors against suicidal thoughts and actions. [70], suggests that promoting resilience may reduce suicide risk in the general population, among those with suicidal ideation, and in high-risk groups for suicide attempt. [71], also believe that most adolescents have the necessary resilience to reduce suicidal thoughts, although it is not definitively known which factors protect against the destructive effect of stress against the emergence of suicidal symptoms following a stressful event. In line with these findings, it seems that the existence of a strong support system can help people to use more mature coping and problem-solving strategies in stressful and critical situations, show more flexibility, cope with challenges and crises better, and finally show more resilience.

In general, PSS can play a vital role in the mental health of adolescents who are deprived of living with their families due to living in daycare centers. PSS can also help them avoid suicidal thoughts. The presence of supportive people as an emotional source can help adolescents cope better with their emotional challenges and problems and manage their negative emotions better. PSS can help this group of adolescents build positive and stable relationships by strengthening their communication and social skills. PSS can help reduce stress and psychological pressure, which can lead to a reduction in negative and suicidal thoughts.

Fourth hypothesis: *PSS mediates the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO.*

The results showed that the PSS mediates the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts in adolescents living in Tehran's SWO. This finding is consistent with the results of others' research [72] regarding the mediating role of perceived PSS in the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts. Based on [72], teacher support and family support mediate the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts. Regardless of gender and age, family support moderates the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts, and EI helps to reduce suicidal thoughts only if there is medium or high family support.

These researchers found that peer support and age moderate the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts. In other words, peer support and age affect the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts, especially for older adolescents. The findings of the present study are also consistent with the results of studies that have confirmed the mediating role of PSS in the relationship between EI and the mental health of adolescents [67] [73 - 75]. For example, [74] showed that perceived PSS plays a mediating role between EI and mental health in undergraduate students. [75], have also shown that PSS and life satisfaction act as mediators in the relationship between EI and depression.

People with high EI traits usually have a greater ability to communicate effectively with others, as a result, they can better understand their own and other people's feelings and establish stronger social relationships. High EI can help people build stronger support networks. People who are better able to manage their emotions tend to be perceived as more reliable friends and colleagues, and this fact can lead to receiving more PSS. Also, people with high EI traits usually have more ability to manage conflicts. They can control negative emotions and solve problems, which helps maintain social relationships and mutual support. In this context, [72], believe that EI in adolescents can help create better PSS to face personal challenges. EI includes the ability to empathize with others. People who can understand the emotions of others are usually more willing to provide PSS and this can help strengthen interpersonal relationships. Therefore, it seems that PSS can help people's mental health and EI can also help people to take advantage of this support. In other words, people with high EI traits can better use their support resources and as a result, they will have better mental health. Effective conflict management reduces stress and anxiety, and the ability to cope effectively with

stress and problems also reduces adolescent depression. Therefore, as mental health increases, suicidal thoughts also decrease.

To understand the mediating role of PSS in the relationship between EI and suicidal thoughts in adolescents, one can pay attention to the research that has investigated the mediating effects of PSS in the relationship between EI and psychological well-being [67], show that resilience, PSS, and social behaviors mediate the relationship between EI and positive (joy, fun, energy) and negative (sadness, fear, anxiety) emotions. Similar findings obtained by [73], suggest that EI helps adolescents receive more PSS, which leads to increased resilience and better psychological well-being. Because inflexibility in thinking, cognitive distortions, and negative attitudes are among the cognitive factors affecting suicidal thoughts [76]. Therefore, it seems that by increasing EI and PSS, cognitive and psychological flexibility is improved and as a result, the risk of suicidal thoughts is also reduced. In this regard, [75], showed that the development of emotional skills can help increase the perceived PSS and in turn, lead to the reduction of obstacles in help-seeking behavior in adolescents. This is because adolescents who lack PSS may avoid receiving help and PSS to deal with negative thoughts related to suicide. Therefore, it seems that adolescents with higher EI develop better social skills; They are more likely to seek PSS, and by seeking help from others, their ability to cope increases, as a result, they are better able to deal with suicidal thoughts. In support of this explanation, one can refer to [77]. They showed that greater exposure to suicide and less PSS were associated with more negative help-seeking beliefs.

Adolescents who are better able to identify, assess, and manage their own and others' emotions may be able to create richer social interactions thanks to active listening, empathy, respect, and mutual assistance. These conditions will be optimal for creating more positive effects and less negative effects, as well as for creating more satisfaction with life and their mental well-being [78, 79]. Reducing anxiety and negative emotions along with increased life satisfaction can reduce the risk of suicidal thoughts in adolescents. In explaining these findings, it can be said that a set of personal characteristics (efficacy, self-esteem, etc.), and social characteristics (PSS, social atmosphere, etc.), can help create a better talent for developing resilience to understand problems. As a result, these characteristics help adolescents perceive problems with optimism, which in turn leads to improved well-being and reduced negative effects of personal events [72]. Therefore, EI can strengthen the social behavior of adolescents and lead to better social relationships and increased life satisfaction.

It seems that the interaction of EI and PSS is a vital factor in promoting resilience against suicide, because the feeling of empathy strengthens components such as care, love, and belonging, increasing self-esteem, increasing the sense of connection, and providing coping resources in challenging times in people. Also, increasing these protective factors can reduce suicidal thoughts and the risk of suicide.

CONCLUSIONS

EI and meaning in life act as protective factors against suicidal ideation. PSS plays a crucial mediating role in reducing suicidal thoughts among adolescents in welfare centers. Interventions focusing on strengthening EI, enhancing meaning in life, and increasing social support can be effective preventive strategies.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization: R.N.Y., R.D.; methodology: R.N.Y., R.D., M.J.R.; analysis: R.N.Y. writing—original draft preparation: R.N.Y.; writing—review and editing, R.D., M.J.R. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This study was extracted from the PhD dissertation of Rezvaneh Namazi Yousefi, approved by the Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. No external funding was received.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to thank all participants and staff of Tehran's SWO centers for their cooperation.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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